

Bioethanol manufacturing from industrial olive pomace slurry through integrated hydrothermal carbonisation and non-conventional yeast-based fermentation processes[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The two-phase olive pomace slurry (TOPS) is the major waste of the olive oil industry. Hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC) has been widely used for the conversion of TOPS into hydrochar, a solid biofuel. The HTC process also co-produces a liquid hydrolysate, whose valorisation has been scarcely investigated. This study focussed on to investigate the composition (reducing sugars, total phenols, acetic acid and furfural) and use of the hydrolysate derived from conventional and microwave assisted HTC of TOPS to produce bioethanol by the fermentation carried out by *Hansenula polymorpha*, a non-conventional yeast. On the basis of holocellulose content (39.12 %) present in dry TOPS, the optimum conditions to achieve a maximum reducing sugar yield of 25.92 % through conventional HTC were 180 °C and 30 min. In the case of microwave HTC, the optimal conditions were 203 °C and 30 min to obtain a maximum reducing sugar yield of 27.88 %. The HTC also produced total phenols (up to 3.30 %), acetic acid (up to 3.33 %), and furfural (up to 1.96 %). In comparison to conventional HTC, the microwave HTC advantage was generation of lower concentrations of fermentation inhibitors. The *H. polymorpha* strain produced maximum overall bioethanol yield of 0.21 g g⁻¹ in case of fermentation of liquid hydrolysate at 45 °C with inoculum concentrations of 0.8 g dm⁻³. These findings emphasised that the HTC of TOPS could be an alternative and promising method for co-production of reducing sugars, bioethanol and total phenols.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) is the leading producer of olive oil in the world, accounting for about 2 million tonnes per year, or 68 % of global output. Within the EU, the main contributors are Spain (66 %), Italy (15 %), Greece (13 %), and Portugal (5 %) [1]. The olive oil industry generates a huge quantity of olive pomace waste, about 800 kg per ton of processed olive oil [2]. It is mainly produced as a by-product during olive oil production through the milling of olive fruit followed mostly by malaxation and two-phase centrifugation processes [3]. This olive pomace is commonly known as a two-phase olive pomace, which contains on average 65 % water content, 2–4 % oil content, pulp, and stones of the olive [4]. It also contains other useful constituents such as arabinose rich pectin, about 30 % potassium, oleanolic and masilinic acids

[5]. The disposal of olive pomace is a challenging issue for olive oil industry due to its acidic pH, high salinity, and high phenolic contents causing phytotoxicity [2]. Valorisation of olive pomace for the production of biofuels and other bioproducts will solve disposal problems and related environmental issues [6]. This will also promote the biorefinery concept and support EU member states to achieve the mandatory target of using 10 % renewable energy in transport (mainly including biofuels) in line with EU Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 [7].

The prevalent strategy for valorisation of two-phase olive pomace is to extract pomace oil and prepare dried pellets of the remaining exhausted (de-oiled) olive pomace for energy generation through combustion, pyrolysis and gasification processes [8–10]. Several industries have been using gasification and combustion of dried olive pomace for

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power generation [11–14]. Application of pyrolysis technology for olive pomace has not been implemented at an industrial scale. These are energy-intensive processes, which requires the drying of wet olive pomace to evaporate high water content [8]. The solvent extraction method was predominantly reported for polyphenols (mainly hydroxytyrosol) extraction from olive pomace for application as antioxidants [15,16]. It was reported that olive pomace contains 98 % of the phenolic compounds of fruit, compared to 2 % in olive oil [17]. The utilisation of two-phase olive pomace was also documented for the production of hydrochar, sugars, and bioethanol [18,19].

Hydrochar is mainly produced through the hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC), which is a less energy-intensive method than pyrolysis and gasification due to the direct use of wet biomass and the elimination of the energy-consuming drying step [20,21]. The HTC of lignocellulosic biomass involved deformation and structural breakdown of the plant cell walls which facilitated the hydrolysis of hemicellulose, partial hydrolysis of cellulose (specifically amorphous cellulose part), and lignin rearrangement [22]. Wet biomass is heated in a subcritical water condition for a few minutes to hours under 180–250 °C temperature and 5–20 MPa pressure [23,24]. During the subcritical conditions of HTC, the hot compressed water decreases its viscosity and dielectric constant and increases the water ionization constant. This led to water acting as an acid catalyst and an effective solvent and reaction medium, which promoted the breakdown of biomass polymeric structure [23]. In conventional HTC, the hot water and lignocellulosic biomass get heated from the outer to the inner part due to heat transfer through a convection-conduction mechanism. Therefore, the outer surface of biomass tends to have a relatively high temperature [25]. Recently, the use of microwave (frequency range: 0.3–300 GHz) assisted HTC reported to have more advantages such as direct non-contact heating, short reaction time (≤ 50 min), and low heating temperature (≤ 200 °C) [26]. In microwave HTC, microwave radiation transforms electromagnetic energy into heat, which causes rapid and uniform heating of biomass [27]. The HTC of lignocellulosic biomass also co-produces a hydrolysate (liquid fraction) rich in several by-products such as hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), furfural, vanillin & phenols [28]. The composition of the hydrolysate is highly variable and dependent on factors including temperature, holding time, pressure, and pH of liquid medium. The longer residence time increased the severity of HTC, which promotes the production of organic acids and the extraction of sugars in the hydrolysate [20,29,30]. Earlier studies mainly documented phenol recovery from olive waste using solvents, and conventional and microwave-based hydrothermal extraction [15,16,31]. Olive waste (including olive pomace) was also reported for the hydrochar production through conventional [31–40] and microwave-assisted HTC [41].

Bioethanol production from lignocellulosic biomass is very challenging due to its recalcitrant structure and cellulose crystallinity [42]. Thus, enzymatic and acid hydrolysis are used for the saccharification of lignocellulosic biomass to produce fermentable sugar, specifically glucose [43]. Enzymatic hydrolysis (cellulase enzymes) is a common method to hydrolyse the cellulosic fractions of biomass into sugars monomers (e.g., hexose, pentose). Fermentation of simple sugars is conventionally done by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast for bioethanol production [44]. The use of expensive enzymes and their non-reusability makes enzymatic hydrolysis highly expensive. Biomass acid hydrolysis also produces toxic & corrosive compounds that inhibit the fermenting yeast's activity, reaction kinetics, and bioethanol yield [45,46]. Water-based hydrothermal pre-treatment, commonly known as autohydrolysis, were reported for bioethanol production due to advantages such as no use of environmentally polluting and corrosive chemicals (organic solvents/acids), but the limitation was that sugar yield was found to be relatively lower [47]. Several researchers studied combinations of autohydrolysis or dilute acid hydrolysis and enzymatic hydrolysis of olive pomace to obtain fermentable sugar to produce bioethanol [48–51]. Tayeh et al. (2014) reported that dilute acid hydrolysis of olive waste at 100 °C for 2 h produced a hydrolysate with

glucose (1.67 g dm⁻³), xylose (8.80 g dm⁻³), acetic acid (2.13 g dm⁻³), formic acid (0.53 g dm⁻³) and furfural (0.056 g dm⁻³). Enzymatic hydrolysis was also performed using cellulases and β -glucosidase mixtures to obtain hydrolysate with more fermentable sugar. The hydrolysates were detoxified using activated carbon to reduce inhibitor content and underwent fermentation by *Issatchenkia orientalis*, which exhibited 3 g bioethanol yield from 100 g dry olive waste [52]. The autohydrolysis of de-oiled olive pomace at 200 °C for 30 min produced the hydrolysate with 3.15 g dm⁻³ reducing sugar concentration. Subsequent enzymatic (Novozyme 188 and Celluclast 1.5 dm⁻³ enzymes) hydrolysis of solids obtained after hydrothermal treatment generated 95.23 % more reducing sugar content. The fermentation of this hydrolysate by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* showed the bioethanol productivity of 0.086 kg m⁻³h⁻¹ [53]. The mixture of olive pomace and olive mill wastewater was pre-treated at 120 °C for 30 min with 0.5 % H₂SO₄ to produce hydrolysate rich in glucose. The *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* fermented this hydrolysate after its lime pre-treatment and produced a maximum ethanol concentration of 10 g dm⁻³ [54].

The main focus of autohydrolysis of olive pomace has been to obtain hydrolysate rich in fermentable sugar for bioethanol production. Details about the residual solid have been seldom documented. In contrast to autohydrolysis, the goal of the HTC has been to produce a hydrochar for several applications, such as biofuel and soil amendment [18]. The HTC process also produced a hydrolysate, which was seldom studied for bioethanol production. In comparison to autohydrolysis, the integration of the one-step HTC method and fermentation could be a better strategy because it has the potential to coproduce hydrochar and a sugar-rich hydrolysate that could be used for bioethanol production. For the first time, the present work evaluates this hypothesis for two-phase olive pomace slurry. The HTC of two-phase olive pomace biomass produces solid (hydrochar), liquid hydrolysate, and gaseous products. The detailed characteristics of hydrochar produced by the conventional and microwave-assisted HTC were reported in our earlier publications [39,41]. These studies reported the hydrochar yield on the basis of dried olive pomace weight ranged from 50 % to 90 %. The higher heating value of the hydrochars were up to 32.2 MJ·kg⁻¹ suitable for biofuel application. In the present work, the gaseous products were not collected and were retained inside the process reactors to maintain autogenic pressure for HTC. For further advancement of fermentation research, the present study also aims to investigate the *Hansenula polymorpha* yeast-based fermentation for the production of bioethanol. *Hansenula polymorpha* is one of the non-conventional yeasts widely reported for its high tolerance to temperature and inhibitors concentrations [55]. The novelty and specific objectives of the present work are: 1) To evaluate the composition of hydrolysate including reducing sugars, total phenols, acetic acid, and furfural produced by both conventional and microwave-assisted water-based HTC of two-phase olive pomace slurry; 2) To assess the performance of *H. polymorpha* strains, identifying best condition (inoculum concentration, and time) for fermentation of olive pomace hydrolysate for bioethanol production.

2. Materials and methodology

2.1. Feedstock collection

The two-phase olive (*Olea europaea L.*) pomace slurry (“Alperujo” in Spanish) was obtained from the Almazara Andrés Aguilar, Linares (Jaén province), Spain. The olive pomace slurry contained 80.43 % moisture content, 28.30 % hemicellulose, and 10.82 % cellulose [39]. In the laboratory, the raw material was stored in a freezer at -40 °C to stop microbial activity, gas formation, and biomass decomposition.

2.2. HTC experiments

The HTC experiments were conducted based on the face-centred central composite design (CCD) with three central points prepared by

response surface methodology, whose details are provided in section 2.5. The CCD uses a second-order quadratic model based on a minimum number of experiments to optimise variables and obtain the best response. It is widely applied both in research and industries as an effective alternative to full-level factorial design that requires a large number of experiments to study the impacts of each variable on responses [56–58]. The CCD experiments were performed both by conventional and microwave-assisted HTC methods with two factors i.e., temperature (180 °C–250 °C) and holding time (2 min–30 min). Details of these methods were described in earlier research publications [39,41]. The CCD with experimental and coded values for HTC experiments was presented in Table S1 (Supplementary Information). The conventional HTC experiments were undertaken in a stirred reactor (Parr 4848, Parr Instrument Company, USA) with 2 dm³ capacity steel vessels. The microwave (1000 W) assisted HTC experiments were done in a microwave digestion system (Milestone Ethos One, Italy) with 10 closed vessels made of Teflon with each 100 cm³ capacity. Maximum autogenic pressures (average values) were different during conventional (14.0 bars, 32.0 bars, 70.0 bars) and microwave (11.4 bars, 26.8 bars, 49.0 bars) HTC experiments at 180 °C, 215 °C and 250 °C, respectively. The difference in pressure in conventional and microwave reactors could be due to different ratio of volume occupied by the pomace to free volume, amount of sample fed and steam generated. The solid and liquid phases (hydrolysate) were separated after the experiment through the vacuum filtration method. The liquid samples were stored in closed glass bottles in a deep freezer at – 40 °C to minimise the degradation of organic compounds. The abbreviations for samples produced under different conditions are Cx–y or Mx–y, where C and M indicate conventional or microwave reactors, respectively, x is the temperature (°C) and y is the holding time (min).

2.3. Fermentation experiments

The wild-type *Hansenula polymorpha* yeast strain (DSM 70277) was acquired from the Leibniz Institute, DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH in Braunschweig, Germany. It was conserved in the autoclaved solid agar media composed of 3 g dm⁻³ yeast extract; 3 g dm⁻³ malt extract; 5 g dm⁻³ peptone; 10 g dm⁻³ xylose; and 20 g dm⁻³ agar-agar [59]. Then, an adapted strain was prepared by the adaptive evolution method [60]. This involved growing the wild-type strain in a 50 cm³ conical flask sealed with a cotton plug and containing 25 cm³ nutrient medium and diluted hydrolysate mixture for 48 h at 35 °C in a thermostat shaker (IKA INC 125 FS Digital, Spain). The liquid medium was made of by mixing 2.0 g dm⁻³ yeast extract, 1.8 g dm⁻³ peptone, 1.5 g dm⁻³ (NH₄)₂SO₄, 1.0 g dm⁻³ MgSO₄·7H₂O, and 1.0 g dm⁻³ KH₂PO₄ in distilled water [61]. A 0.25 cm³ aliquot was transferred to new flasks with a gradual increase in concentration of hydrolysate. This process was repeated multiple times (20 cycles) to prepare an adapted strain of *H. polymorpha* to improve its growth in the hydrolysate.

The adapted strain was used for the fermentation of hydrolysate to produce bioethanol, and xylitol. The fermentation experiments were conducted in aforesaid thermostat shaker using 250 cm³ conical flasks with caps and provisions to collect samples periodically through syringes. Experiments were performed for different inoculum concentrations (0.1 g dm⁻³ to 1.3 g dm⁻³), temperatures (35 °C to 45 °C), and time (0 h to 92.5 h). The CCD with experimental and coded values for fermentation experiments was presented in Table S2 (Supplementary Information). A fixed pH of 5.5 and a mixture of 75 % concentrated hydrolysate and 25 % nutrient media were used for the fermentation. External aeration was not provided during the experiment. The yeasts were dependent on the dissolved oxygen (3.81 mg dm⁻³) present in the hydrolysate. The spectrophotometric method was used for estimating the yeast biomass concentration (g dm⁻³) on the basis of a calibration curve prepared using the optical density value (620 nm) and yeast biomass oven-dried weight (g). The concentrations of dissolved oxygen

(DO) in the fermentation medium were determined with the optical dissolved oxygen instrument (HI-98198, Hanna Instruments Ltd., UK).

The maximum specific growth rate and volumetric productivity of the yeast were calculated using Equations (1) and (2), respectively. In Equation (1), 'μ_m' is maximum rate of specific growth, h⁻¹; 'x' is cell concentration per volume at varied time (t); 'x₀' is cell concentration at the initial time (t = 0); 'a' is empirical constant that represents the change in growth rate with time. The 'μ_m' and 'a' are the values of slope and intercept respectively, derived from the linear plot between 't' and 'ln (x/x₀)' for exponential growth phase. In Equation (2), 'P_b' is volumetric productivity (g·dm⁻³·h⁻¹), and 'c' is empirical constant for relation between volumetric productivity and time [59,62]. The empirical constants are numerical values derived from experimental data to fit the equation and calculate the desired parameters such as μ_m and P_b.

$$\ln\left(\frac{x}{x_0}\right) = \mu_m t + a \quad (1)$$

$$x = c + P_b t \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{x/s}^o = \frac{dx}{d(s_0 - s)} \quad (3)$$

Overall biomass yield (Y_{x/s}^o), measured as per Equation (3), is a quotient among net biomass produced and net substrate uptake. In this equation, Y_{x/s}^o is slope value, calculated based on the values of x – x₀ versus s₀ – s [59].

The specific substrate (TRS) uptake rate (q_s) was determined transforming the Equation (4) in linear form and performing least square adjustments. Where 's' is the substrate uptake at a definite time; 's₀' is the substrate uptake at starting time (t = 0); 'α' and 'β' are empirical constants indicated the change in substrate uptake rate with time. The specific ethanol production rate (q_{et}) is calculated by differential treatment of the kinetic linear Equation (5), where x_{et} is bioethanol concentration, 'a' and 'b' are empirical constants representing the change in ethanol production with time. The overall bioethanol yield (Y_{et}^o) was calculated using Equation (6) [59]. In Equation (6), et = bioethanol concentration; Y_{et}^o is overall bioethanol yield calculated from the values of et – et₀ (t = 0) versus s₀ (t = 0) – s. Similarly, instantaneous product yield (Y_{et}) is determined using the values of et – et₀ (t = 0) versus x – x₀ (t = 0).

$$s = s_0 \alpha^{-t^\beta} \quad (4)$$

$$x_{et} = a' + b't \quad (5)$$

$$Y_{et}^o = \frac{d_{et} - d_{et\ at\ 0}}{d(s_0 - s)} \quad (6)$$

2.4. Analysis of liquid samples

Miller's method (1959) was used to analyse total reducing sugar (TRS) in hydrolysates, with dinitrosalicylic acid reagent [63]. The monosaccharides concentrations were measured using an ion chromatograph equipped with a Metrosep Carb 2 100/4.0 IC column (Carb 2 150/4.0) and a pulsed amperometric detector (930 Compact IC Flex, Metrohm AG, Switzerland). The aforementioned sugar were acquired from Sigma Aldrich (Merck, Germany) and utilised to create the calibration curve. The eluent for ion chromatography was a mixture of 100 mM NaOH and 10 mM sodium acetate solution provided by Metrohm AG (Herisau, Switzerland). Acetic acid was tested using an enzymatic method (Enzytec™ Liquid Acetic Acid E8226, R-Biopharm AG, Germany). Total phenols were determined spectrophotometrically using the Folin-Calcateu reagent and expressed as gallic acid equivalent [64]. The ethanol concentrations were determined using gas chromatography (Shimadzu 2010 Plus, Japan) with an FID detector and BPX5 capillary column. Helium was employed as a carrier gas, with a flow rate of 50

Fig. 1. TRS contents in the hydrolysate and conversion yields of TRS on basis of holocellulose content of dried olive pomace for samples produced by microwave and conventional HTC.

$\text{cm}^3\text{min}^{-1}$. Sample analysis was carried out using an external ethanol (GC standard, Sigma Aldrich, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) for the calibration, an analytical column temperature of 55 °C, a pressure level of 100 kPa, and an oven temperature of 70 °C. Xylitol concentrations were determined using an enzymatic test (Cat. No. 10670057035; R-BIOPHARM, Germany).

2.5. Response surface design analysis

Modde 6.0 software (Umetric AB, Sweden) was used to prepare CCD for HTC and fermentation, and subsequent data analysis on the basis of a second-order polynomial model (Equation – 7) involving two independent variables (IV_1 and IV_2) and responses (Yield for TRS, total phenols, and ethanol). The independent variables (IV_1 and IV_2) were temperature (T) and holding time (t), respectively, for HTC experiments; while for fermentation assays IV_1 was the inoculum concentration (IC) and IV_2 was the bioprocess time (t).

$$Y = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 \cdot IV_1) + (\beta_2 \cdot IV_2) + (\beta_3 \cdot IV_1 \cdot IV_1) + (\beta_4 \cdot IV_2 \cdot IV_2) + (\beta_5 \cdot IV_1 \cdot IV_2) \quad (7)$$

where Y is the response value, IV_1 and IV_2 are the real values of the two independent variables, and β_i ($i = 1-5$) are the intercept term (β_0), the linear effects (β_1 and β_2), the squared effects (β_3 and β_4), and the interaction effects (β_5) calculated from the experimental data by regression analysis. The experimental data validation was performed by a one-way ANOVA statistical test with a 95 % confidence level.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Reducing sugar production

The average values (with standard deviations) for TRS contents, its conversion yield (based on holocellulose fraction of dried olive pomace), and concentrations of glucose, fructose, xylose, sucrose, and lactose present in the hydrolysate produced by conventional and microwave-assisted HTC of olive pomace slurry are presented in Table S3 (Supplementary information). In addition, the TRS contents and its conversion yields for HTC samples are also shown in Fig. 1. The HTC and treatment conditions (temperature and holding time) impacted the generation of TRS. The variations were also observed for TRS between hydrolysates produced by microwave and conventional HTC at same temperatures and holding time. This could be due to their non-uniform

Fig. 2. Concentrations mg g^{-1} of glucose, fructose, sucrose, xylose and lactose in the hydrolysate samples produced by microwave and conventional HTC.

autogenic pressures (mentioned in section 2.2). In contrast to microwave HTC, the autogenic pressures were relatively higher in conventional HTC due to conduction–convection heating mechanism and use of larger reactor vessel. It influenced the HTC process severity and several simultaneous reactions such as hydrolysis of polysaccharides and oligosaccharides into TRS, and its transformation into organic acids and furfural. When the HTC temperature reaches 180 °C, the hemicellulose depolymerizes into oligosaccharides by proton-catalysed cleavage of glycosidic bonds, which hydrolyse into glucose, fructose, and other monosaccharides (e.g., hexoses, pentoses, etc.). The amorphous cellulose fractions depolymerise above 210 °C, resulting in oligosaccharides and cellobiose, which are subsequently hydrolysed to produce monosaccharides such as glucose and fructose. The crystalline cellulose remains resistant to hydrolysis by hot compressed water [74]. A balance between degradation and hydrolysis reactions during HTC is necessary to achieve higher TRS yields. The concentrations of TRS (per g dry olive pomace) were generally higher in the hydrolysate produced by microwave HTC (49.44 mg g^{-1} – 107.13 mg g^{-1}) than conventional HTC (40.54 mg g^{-1} – 101.20 mg g^{-1}). In comparison to present results, Yuan et al. (2019) also found TRS yields of 118.57 mg g^{-1} to 120.33 mg g^{-1} from tobacco waste (leaf and stem) by microwave-assisted hydrothermal treatment [65]. The conversion yields for TRS based on the dried weight of olive pomace were 4.94 %–10.71 % and 4.05 %–10.12 %, whereas based on holocellulose content (39.12 %) of olive pomace, TRS conversion yields were 12.64 %–27.38 % and 10.36 %–25.87 % for

Fig. 3. Total phenols, acetic acid and furfural concentrations (%) in the hydrolysate samples produced by the microwave and conventional HTC.

microwave HTC and conventional HTC, respectively. The influence of holding time on TRS was observed to be different at specific HTC temperatures. The TRS yields increased with prolongation of holding time from 2 min to 30 min for microwave HTC at 180 °C and 215 °C, and for conventional HTC at 180 °C. In contrast, TRS yields reduced with an increase in holding time at 250 °C with microwave HTC and at 215 °C and 250 °C with conventional HTC. The maximum TRS yield was 25.87 % in case of conventional HTC at 180 °C for 30 min. Comparatively, the microwave HTC at 215 °C for 30 min produced more TRS yield (27.38 %).

The concentrations of glucose, fructose, lactose, xylose, and sucrose on basis of dried olive pomace are presented in Fig. 2. The maximum concentrations of glucose were in M215-16 (5.98 mg g⁻¹), fructose in C250-2 (8.18 mg g⁻¹), sucrose (2.86 mg g⁻¹) and xylose (2.65 mg g⁻¹) in C180-30, and lactose (3.98 mg g⁻¹) in M250-2 hydrolysates. The microwave HTC from 180 °C-2 min to 215 °C-16 min resulted into enrichment of glucose concentrations (2.97 mg g⁻¹–5.98 mg g⁻¹). The glucose concentrations were 36.95 % higher with microwave HTC at 215 °C-16 min compared to maximum glucose concentration of 3.77 mg g⁻¹ obtained with conventional HTC at 180 °C for 2 min. Fan et al. (2013) also reported that microwave-assisted hydrothermal treatment of cellulose yielded 1.2 % more glucose obtained with conventional HTC at 220 °C [75]. However, microwave HTC post 215 °C-16 min and conventional HTC post 180-2 min treatment conditions exhibited decreasing trend for the glucose concentrations. But the fructose concentrations were elevated in those conditions and the glucose concentrations diminished specifically in M250-16, M250-30, C215-2, C215-16, C215-30, C250-2, C250-16 and C250-30. This difference could be due to the isomerization of glucose into fructose during those HTC conditions [66,67]. The isomerization can take place by two pathways, based on Brønsted base catalysis (also known as Lobry de Bruyn-van Ekenstein rearrangement) [68,69] and Lewis acid catalysis [70]. The first pathway involved the interaction of the glucose with a Brønsted base (as a proton acceptor) that formed a 1,2-enediol intermediate. Thereafter, subsequent transfer of a proton from O-2 to O-1 and C-2 to C-1 led to fructose formation. In the case of the second pathway, the Lewis acid sites, with the help of their lone electron pair, interacted with O-1 of the glucose and polarized the C=O bond. The same acid sites engaged with the O-2 atom, which created a complex and caused a shift of intramolecular hydrogen from C-2 to C-1, resulting in the fructose production [71–73]. The formation of Lewis acids (phenols and acetic acids) in hydrolysate and their cumulative impact during HTC could be the reason for isomerisation of glucose to fructose, observed in this study. However, to support this reason more detailed study on specific mechanisms are required.

Fig. 4. Average values of DO consumption by *H. polymorpha* strains under different fermentation conditions. Adapted strain led fermentation at 40 °C with: a) 0.8 g dm⁻³ inoculum, b) 0.1 g dm⁻³ inoculum, c) 1.3 g dm⁻³ inoculum in hydrolysate and, d) 0.1 g dm⁻³ inoculum in pure sugar (glucose + xylose); e) 0.8 g dm⁻³ inoculum in hydrolysate at 35 °C fermentation; f) wild type strain with 0.8 g dm⁻³ inoculum in hydrolysate at 40 °C; g) wild type strain with 0.1 g dm⁻³ inoculum in pure sugar (glucose + xylose) at 40 °C; h) Adapted strain with 0.8 g dm⁻³ inoculum in hydrolysate at 45 °C.

3.2. Total phenols, acetic acid and furfural production

The concentrations of total phenols, acetic acid, and furfural in the hydrolysate produced by the conventional and microwave HTC are shown in Fig. 3. Total phenols were inherently present in the slurry of the olive pomace, which increased further specifically at higher HTC temperature due to depolymerization of lignin. Acetic acid was formed from the cleavage of acetyl groups in hemicellulose fractions (Li et al., 2015) and furfural was formed due to the thermal dehydration of saccharides (specifically pentoses like xylose) during HTC [76]. In general, the HTC in a microwave reactor generated relatively lower total phenols (1.66 %–2.88 %), acetic acid (0.27 %–2.09 %), and furfural contents (0.08 %–0.33 %) than conventional HTC (1.24 %–3.30 % total phenols, 0.54 %–3.33 % acetic acid, 0.20 %–1.96 % furfural). Increasing the HTC temperature from 180 °C to 250 °C resulted in the production of more total phenols, acetic acid, and furfural. The escalation in HTC holding time from 2 min to 30 min at specific temperatures enhanced the formation of furfural. However, there was a non-uniform impact of holding time on the total phenols and acetic acid. The use of a conventional pressure reactor produced higher total phenols (3.30 %) at 250 °C-2 min, acetic acid (3.33 %) at 250 °C-30 min, and furfural (1.96 %) at 250 °C-30 min. In the case of the microwave reactor, maximum concentrations of total phenols (2.88 %) were generated at 250 °C-30 min, acetic acid (2.09 %) at 250 °C-2 min, and furfural (0.37 %) at 250 °C-30 min. Formation of acetic acid led to a decrease in pH from 5 (two-phase olive pomace slurry) to 3 (hydrolysate from HTC).

Phaiboonsilpa et al. (2020) also documented that hydrothermal treatment at a higher temperature of 250 °C produced more organic acids and furfural formed by the decomposition of xylose, oligosaccharides, glucose, and arabinose [77]. During HTC, the lignin undergoes hydrolysis, partial cleavage of β-O-4, ether bonds, aliphatic C – C bonds cleavage, alkylation, and demethoxylation. The lignin depolymerizes above 210 °C into an aromatic oligomer, and its hydrolysis produces phenol compounds and methoxylated benzenes. The hydrolysate of lignin contained phenol, cresol, catechol, and guaiacol. An increase in temperature causes more production of alkyl-substituted phenols from methoxyl aromatic products [78,79]. In contrast to the present results, Gimenez et al. (2020) reported a higher total phenols content of 3.58 % in hydrolysate obtained from HTC of two-phase olive pomace at 240 °C

Fig. 5. Growth curve (based on average values) of adapted *H. polymorpha* with a) different inoculum concentrations and b) fermentation temperatures, c) Wild type versus adapted strains, d) Pure sugar (glucose + xylose) versus hydrolysate.

for 4 h. This difference was due to the use of longer residence time for HTC. Generally, hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol were the main phenolic compounds found in the olive pomace hydrolysate [31]. Overall, the experimental results highlighted that microwave HTC was suitable for obtaining relatively higher TRS and lower contents of inhibitors (total phenols, acetic acid, and furfural). However, the conventional HTC was found more suitable for more transformation of sugar to acetic acid and furfural.

3.3. Fermentation of hydrolysate

3.3.1. DO consumption

The consumption of DO after 92.5 h fermentation of hydrolysate and pure sugars (glucose and xylose in 1:1 ratio) by wild type and adapted strains of *H. polymorpha* are shown in Fig. 4. Adapted strains of *H. polymorpha* were obtained through adaptive evolution using

hydrolysate. The DO consumption by adapted *H. polymorpha* strains were relatively lower (75.7 %) in fermentation of hydrolysate with 1.3 g dm⁻³ inoculum at 40 °C and 0.8 g dm⁻³ inoculum at 35 °C. Increasing the fermentation temperature from 35 °C to 40 °C, accelerated the DO consumption from 75.7 % to 84.9 %, but further increase of fermentation temperature to 45 °C reduced the DO consumption to 83.3 %. The inoculum of 0.1 g dm⁻³ adapted strain showed the highest DO consumption of 95.7 % in case of fermentation of pure sugars. Whereas, in same conditions for fermentation of hydrolysate, the DO consumption was 91.2 %. The use of low inoculum concentration (0.1 g dm⁻³) exhibited more DO consumption compared to high inoculum (1.3 g dm⁻³). The consumption of DO for fermentation of hydrolysate by wild type strain was relatively higher (90.0 %) than adapted strain (84.9 %). Overall, the above results exhibited the ability of *H. polymorpha* strain under limited oxygen presence, which is in agreement with previous studies [59,80].

Table 1

Biomass volumetric productivity (P_b), Maximum specific growth rate (μ_m), Specific growth rate (q_s), overall biomass yield (Y_s^0), instantaneous bioethanol yield (Y_{et}), overall bioethanol yield (Y_{et}^Q), specific ethanol production rate (q_{et}) for the fermentation of hydrolysate and pure sugar by *H. polymorpha* strains. Fermentation parameters included temperature, inoculum concentrations and strain type.

Fermentation parameters	P_b (g dm ⁻³ h ⁻¹)	μ_m (h ⁻¹)	q_s (g·g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	Y_s^0 (g g ⁻¹)	Y_{et} (g dm ⁻³)	Y_{et}^Q (g g ⁻¹)	q_{et} (g·g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)
Hydrolysate fermentation							
35 °C, 0.8 g dm ⁻³ , wild type strain	0.057 ± 0.001	0.042 ± 0.00	0.10 ± 0.01	0.296 ± 0.007	0.51 ± 0.05	0.11 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.00
35 °C, 0.8 g dm ⁻³ , Adapted strain	0.031 ± 0.003	0.039 ± 0.001	0.43 ± 0.06	0.048 ± 0.009	0.84 ± 0.08	0.13 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.00
40 °C, 0.8 g dm ⁻³ , Adapted strain	0.025 ± 0.001	0.029 ± 0.004	0.31 ± 0.01	0.060 ± 0.016	0.63 ± 0.15	0.09 ± 0.03	0.02 ± 0.01
45 °C, 0.8 g dm ⁻³ , Adapted strain	0.017 ± 0.000	0.026 ± 0.007	0.40 ± 0.04	0.105 ± 0.027	2.50 ± 0.25	0.21 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.01
40 °C, 0.1 g dm ⁻³ , Adapted strain	0.043 ± 0.003	0.086 ± 0.003	0.23 ± 0.06	0.170 ± 0.016	0.50 ± 0.10	0.05 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01
40 °C, 1.3 g dm ⁻³ , Adapted strain	0.050 ± 0.008	0.027 ± 0.004	0.06 ± 0.01	0.211 ± 0.034	0.43 ± 0.04	0.06 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.00
Pure sugar fermentation							
40 °C, 0.1 g dm ⁻³ , pure sugar, wild type strain	0.152 ± 0.005	0.165 ± 0.010	0.08 ± 0.01	0.320 ± 0.015	1.50 ± 0.025	0.39 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.06
40 °C, 0.1 g dm ⁻³ , pure sugar, Adapted strain	0.104 ± 0.001	0.109 ± 0.005	0.13 ± 0.01	0.198 ± 0.031	1.30 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.03	0.14 ± 0.00

3.3.2. Yeast growth and production of bioethanol

Bioethanol is produced by yeast from glucose and xylose through two different pathways. The glucose is biologically converted into bioethanol through the Embden–Meyerhof–Parnas pathway. On the other hand, xylose is first converted to xylulose, and it is converted into bioethanol through the pentose phosphate pathway [81]. In this study, *H. polymorpha* was selected for bioethanol production because it is a thermotolerant yeast and favours the fermentation of varied sugars such as glucose, xylose and cellobiose. The *H. polymorpha* developed tolerance to high temperature (up to 50 °C) due to synthesis and accumulation of trehalose, a thermo-protective compound [82]. It is also resistant to inhibitors present in the hydrolysate [83]. The application of the adaptive evolution method was done to make *H. polymorpha* more inhibitor-resistant. The hydrolysate used for fermentation contained about 22.79 g dm⁻³ of TRS, 1.80 g dm⁻³ of total phenols, 0.64 g dm⁻³ of furfural, and 1.29 g dm⁻³ of acetic acid. Fig. 5 presents the influence of fermentation parameters on the growth of the adapted *H. polymorpha* strain. The temperature, inoculum concentrations, and time impacted the performance of the adapted yeast strain, fermentation process, and bioethanol production (Table 1). In addition to bioethanol, the xylitol was also coproduced at 20 h fermentation time, 0.06 g dm⁻³ with pure sugar, and with hydrolysate ranged from 0.03 g dm⁻³ to 0.04 g dm⁻³.

3.3.2.1. Impact of temperature. During fermentation experiments, the yeast growth curve mostly exhibited a lag phase from 0 to 7 h and an exponential phase from 7 to 23 h. The elevation in temperature from 35 °C to 45 °C caused the reduction in the P_b (from 0.031 g·dm⁻³h⁻¹ to 0.017 g·dm⁻³h⁻¹), but showed a rise in the μ_m (0.026 h⁻¹ to 0.039 h⁻¹). Furthermore, the q_s was 0.43 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ at 35 °C, 0.31 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ at 40 °C, and 0.40 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ at 45 °C. The Y_s^o increased from 0.048 g g⁻¹ to 0.105 g g⁻¹. The temperatures of 35 °C and 40 °C showed the 0.61 g dm⁻³ bioethanol production, with the difference in time, i.e., 40 h and 25 h, respectively. Whereas, the temperature of 45 °C produced more bioethanol of 1.88 g dm⁻³ at 40 h. These results indicated that the yeast was not only thermotolerant but also produced relatively higher bioethanol at higher temperatures. The fermentation time of 40 h was found to be suitable for achieving a higher yield with 35 °C and 45 °C temperatures. Whereas, 25 h was appropriate to obtain a higher bioethanol yield at 40 °C temperature. Increase in Y_{et}^o (0.09 g g⁻¹ to 0.21 g g⁻¹) and q_{et} (0.02 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ to 0.06 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹) also observed by increase in temperature to 45 °C. The Y_{et} were 0.84 g dm⁻³, 0.63 g dm⁻³, and 2.50 g dm⁻³ for fermentation at 35 °C, 40 °C, and 45 °C. A previous study by Martinez et al. (2019) also reported high Y_{et}^o (0.12 g g⁻¹) at the higher temperature of 50 °C [62]. The Y_{et}^o observed in the present study was higher than earlier findings by Martinez et al. (2012), which reported a Y_{et}^o of 0.14 g g⁻¹ by *H. polymorpha* from the fermentation of sunflower stalk hydrolysates [55]. However, in comparison to *H. polymorpha*, the earlier study reported very high Y_{et}^o of 0.46 g g⁻¹ by *Kluyveromyces marxianus* yeast-fermented after 72 h at 42 °C of hydrolysate derived from dilute sulphuric acid hydrolysis (130 °C) enzymatic (cellulase) hydrolysis of extracted olive pomace [51].

3.3.2.2. Impact of inoculum concentrations. The utilisation of more inoculum concentrations from 0.1 g dm⁻³ to 1.3 g dm⁻³ improved the P_b from 0.043 g dm⁻³h⁻¹ to 0.050 g dm⁻³h⁻¹. The lower inoculum concentrations of 0.1 g dm⁻³ exhibited higher μ_m of 0.086 h⁻¹ than 0.029 h⁻¹ and 0.027 h⁻¹ observed for the 0.8 g dm⁻³ and 1.3 g dm⁻³, respectively. In addition, with an increase in inoculum from 0.1 g dm⁻³ to 1.3 g dm⁻³, the q_s reduced from 0.23 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ to 0.06 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹, while Y_s^o increased from 0.170 g g⁻¹ to 0.211 g g⁻¹. Guzmán et al. (2024) also reported that a lower inoculum of yeast resulted in higher Y_s^o [84]. The inoculum concentration of 0.8 g dm⁻³ produced 0.61 g dm⁻³ bioethanol at 25 h time compared to 0.52 g dm⁻³ bioethanol obtained by a 0.1 g dm⁻³ inoculum concentration at 23 h and 0.35 g dm⁻³ bioethanol obtained by 1.3 g dm⁻³ inoculum concentrations at 20 h. The Y_{et} was

higher (0.63 g dm⁻³) with 0.8 g dm⁻³ inoculum concentrations than 0.1 g dm⁻³ (0.50 g dm⁻³) and 1.3 g dm⁻³ (0.43 g dm⁻³). Higher Y_{et}^o was observed with the inoculum concentration of 0.8 g dm⁻³ (0.09 g g⁻¹) in comparison to 1.3 g dm⁻³ (0.06 g g⁻¹) and 0.1 g dm⁻³ (0.05 g g⁻¹). The q_{et} gradually decreased with an increase in inoculum concentrations of 0.1 g dm⁻³ (0.04 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹), 0.8 g dm⁻³ (0.02 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹), and 1.3 g dm⁻³ (0.01 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹).

3.3.2.3. Wild type versus adapted yeast strain performance. In the case of pure sugar (glucose + xylose) fermentation, the wild type yeast strain had a relatively higher μ_m (0.165 h⁻¹), P_b (0.152 g dm⁻³h⁻¹), Y_s^o (0.320 g g⁻¹), Y_{et} (1.50 g dm⁻³), Y_{et}^o (0.39 g g⁻¹), and q_{et} (0.25 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹) than adapted strain with $\mu_m = 0.109$ h⁻¹, $P_b = 0.104$ g dm⁻³h⁻¹, $Y_s^o = 0.198$ g g⁻¹, $Y_{et} = 1.30$ g dm⁻³, $Y_{et}^o = 0.31$ g g⁻¹, and $q_{et} = 0.14$ g·g⁻¹h⁻¹. The adapted strain demonstrated higher q_s (0.13 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹) compared to wild type strain ($q_s = 0.08$ g·g⁻¹h⁻¹). In comparison with present results, previous study reported fermentation of xylose by the *H. polymorpha* yeast strain showed μ_m of 0.05 h⁻¹, Y_s^o of 0.44 g g⁻¹, and Y_{et}^o of 0.08 g g⁻¹ [85]. However, similar to present results, another non-conventional yeast, *Spathaspora passalidarum* was earlier reported for ethanol yield of 0.40 g g⁻¹ from fermentation of 25 g dm⁻³ of xylose with a 0.5 g dm⁻³ inoculum at 30 °C [84].

In case of fermentation of hydrolysate, the wild-type yeast strain exhibited relatively higher P_b (0.057 g dm⁻³h⁻¹) and μ_m (0.042 h⁻¹) than adapted strain ($P_b = 0.031$ g dm⁻³h⁻¹, $\mu_m = 0.039$ h⁻¹). In contrast, the adapted strain showed more q_s (0.43 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹), Y_s^o (0.048 g g⁻¹), Y_{et} (0.84 g dm⁻³), Y_{et}^o (0.13 g g⁻¹), and q_{et} (0.03 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹) compared to the wildtype strain ($q_s = 0.10$ g·g⁻¹h⁻¹; $Y_s^o = 0.296$ g g⁻¹; $Y_{et} = 0.51$ g dm⁻³; $Y_{et}^o = 0.11$ g g⁻¹; $q_{et} = 0.02$ g·g⁻¹h⁻¹). In a prior study, fermentation of clarified wheat straw hydrolysate (containing 6.50 g dm⁻³ acetic acid and 1.87 g dm⁻³ total phenols) by the *H. polymorpha* strain showed μ_m of 0.06 h⁻¹, Y_s^o of 0.54 g g⁻¹, and Y_{et}^o of 0.11 g g⁻¹ [85]. These findings agreed with the present study findings.

Overall, the growth of both the wild type and adapted strains of *H. polymorpha* were found to be impacted by the presence of inhibitors in the hydrolysate. The adapted *H. polymorpha* strains showed improved substrate consumption rate and inhibitor tolerance compared to wild-type strains. In case of fermentation with pure sugars and without inhibitors, growth of these strains started declining after 55 h. However, with hydrolysate fermentation, these strains were able to tolerate the inhibitors for up to 29 h and afterwards showed a sharp decline in growth. The inhibitor tolerance of *H. polymorpha* was short-lived and dependent on the fermentation time. It is commonly known that the inhibitors stop the growth of microorganisms by causing oxidative stress and cellular damage, specifically by the formation of reactive oxygen species [86]. For the time period of 29 h of hydrolysate fermentation, the *H. polymorpha* strains scavenged oxidative stress by the help of metabolites such as superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione. Superoxide dismutase and catalase are enzymes which scavenge reactive oxygen species and protect yeast cells by maintaining cellular redox homeostasis [87–89]. Glutathione is a non-enzymatic metabolite that functions as a major buffer for cellular redox and counteracts reactive oxygen species [90]. Yeasts also possess the ability to detoxify major inhibitors such as polyphenols, acetic acid, and furfural. The yeasts degrade polyphenols by the help of phenol monooxygenase and catechol dioxygenase enzymes [91,92]. The cells of yeasts can neutralise the weak organic acids like acetic acids by enhancing the generation of plasma membrane transporters that remove the acid anions from cells [93]. Detoxification of furfural by yeasts occurred by reducing it into furfuryl alcohol using NADH and NADPH [94,95]. However, despite the inhibitor tolerance and detoxification capacity of yeast, in present study it was observed that the presence of inhibitors has limited their capacity to achieve high bioethanol yield.

3.4. Process optimisation by response surface analysis

The coefficient values, F value, and p values derived from the second-order polynomial model (Equation (7)) for response surface preparation and to predict optimum conditions for TRS yield, total phenols, and bioethanol are presented in Table 2. The phenols were found to be major inhibitors with relatively high concentrations in the hydrolysate and hence included for response surface optimisation, as it could be an important co-product. The high values for R^2 predicted (0.957–0.994),

R^2 adjusted (0.915–0.988), F value (22.418–169.572), and low p-value (0.000–0.002) emphasised that the quadratic models for TRS, total phenols, bioethanol were statistically significant. The TRS and total phenols production were influenced by the time and temperature. Likewise, the fermentation time and inoculum concentration impacted the ethanol production.

Response surfaces graphs showing optimal conditions to achieve maximum yield of reducing sugars, and total phenols production are shown in Fig. 6. Similarly, the response surface graph depicting

Table 2

Model parameters (based on equation (7)) for TRS conversion efficiency and total phenols by conventional (C) and microwave (M) hydrothermal carbonisation, and ethanol production.

Parameters	C-TRS	M-TRS	C-Total Phenols	M-Total Phenols	Bioethanol
β_0	322.0	-310.0	11.0	3.34	1.06
β_1	-2.82	3.05	-0.106	-0.0203	0.666
β_2	1.12	1.55	0.0289	-0.0728	-0.0356
β_3	0.006	-0.007	0.0003	0.0000657	-0.526
β_4	-0.00456	0.00555	0.00172	0.00105	0.000292
β_5	-0.00454	-0.00778	-0.000469	0.000230	0.00194
P value (regression)	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000
F value (Regression)	170.0	31.5	90.1	22.4	135.0
R^2 predicted	0.994	0.969	0.989	0.957	0.993
R^2 Adjusted	0.988	0.938	0.978	0.915	0.985

Fig. 6. Response surface plots representing the effect of temperature and time on TRS yield and total phenols using conventional HTC (A) and microwave assisted HTC (B).

Fig. 7. Response surface plot representing the effect of inoculum concentration and time on bioethanol production.

optimum conditions for maximum bioethanol production is shown in Fig. 7. The optimum conditions to achieve maximum TRS yield value of 25.92 % through conventional HTC is 180 °C and 30 min. In case of microwave HTC, the optimal conditions were 203 °C and 30 min to obtain maximum TRS yield of 27.88 %. The impact of HTC reactor was evident, which showed that due to high pressure in conventional system, maximum TRS conversion could be achieved at lower temperature compared to microwave system. However, the differences between optimal temperatures for conventional and microwave was very narrow, about 20 °C. On the other hand, the conventional HTC at 250 °C for 2 min was predicted to be optimum conditions to produce 3.29 % of total phenols. For microwave HTC, 250 °C and 30 min were optimal conditions to obtain 2.85 % total phenols in the hydrolysate. The optimum conditions to achieve maximum bioethanol concentration of 0.59 g dm⁻³ were 0.68 g dm⁻³ inoculum and 25 h fermentation time. Under these optimum conditions, the validation experiments produced the bioethanol concentration of 0.53 g dm⁻³, which was very close to the predicted value by the response surface model.

The integration of HTC and the fermentation method adapted in the present work for the valorisation of two-phase olive pomace slurry were effective for the production of hydrolysate with high reducing sugar, phenol and acetic acid concentrations. However, the concentrations of glucose, a preferred fermentable sugar for the yeast, were comparatively low in the hydrolysate and could be the reason for the low bioethanol yield. The application of the adapted *H. polymorpha* strain exhibited an enhanced substrate (present in hydrolysate) consumption rate, but the overall bioethanol yield was found to be 46 % lower compared to control conditions (glucose + xylose sugar and without inhibitors). This highlighted that enrichment of glucose and inhibitors' removal from the hydrolysate would be necessary. Therefore, the post-hydrolysis to enrich glucose and pre-treatment of olive pomace hydrolysate with CaCO₃ could be applied to achieve higher ethanol yield [54]. Alternatively, the future research focus of the integrated HTC and fermentation method can be shifted to produce biochemicals, i.e., organic acids and

polyphenols.

4. Conclusions

Hydrothermal carbonisation of two-phase olive pomace slurry produced a liquid fraction containing reducing sugars, phenols, acetic acid and furfural. Compared to the conventional system, microwave-assisted hydrothermal carbonisation generated a lower concentration of phenols, acetic acid, and furfural due to the lower process severity. Thus, the reducing sugar produced by that method was found suitable for fermentation. The hydrothermal carbonisation temperature of 250 °C was found inappropriate for achieving extraction of high reducing sugars. *H. Polymorpha* strain was able to grow on the hydrolysate in the temperature range 35 °C to 45 °C and with high concentrations of inhibitors. The bioethanol production was maximum at high fermentation temperature of 45 °C. Xylitol was also formed by the yeast during fermentation through the xylose phosphate pathway. The adapted *H. polymorpha* strains prepared by adaptive evolution showed better substrate uptake rate in hydrolysate than the wild type. But the bioethanol yield was marginally higher by the adapted strains compared to wild type strain. Overall, the adaptive evolution was found to be a functional strategy to improve yeast strain for more bioethanol yield production. However, it is necessary to conduct future research on the neutralising the influence of specific inhibitors present in the hydrolysate to substantially enhance the bioethanol yield.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adnan Asad Karim: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Visualization, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Resources, Investigation, Data curation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Maria Lourdes Martínez-Cartas:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Resources,

Investigation, Data curation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Manuel Cuevas-Aranda**: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2025.101128>.

Data availability

Extended dataset with the present manuscript title is available under “OliPFUEL community” of the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101062601/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>).

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